

Creating Unique Polygons with Each Fourier Transform 개별 푸리에 변환을 통해 고유한 다각형 만들기

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2024. 7. 20

Abstract

[한글] 모든 다각형은 푸리에 변환을 통해 정의 가능하다. 이때 도출된 푸리에 변환을 통해 고유한 격자들을 생성할 수 있다.

[English] Any polygon can be defined with Fourier Transform. With each unique Fourier transformation, unique lattices can be generated.

1 Introduction

All the notations and preconditions follow the book referenced[DC16, Cro16, 김11, FB20, Rud76]. It is well known that all the exterior angles in any polygon has sum total of 360 degrees.

2 Each Fourier Transform to Unique Polygon

So it is possible to draw unique polygon with each fourier transform with the number of frequencies as the number of vertices.

3 Lattices Generated with Each Fourier Transform

Ordering the angles in order, mesh comes out:

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